

**Geoffrey Khan, Regius
Professor of Hebrew,
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Open access means actual dissemination

– Geoffrey Kahn

Publishing books open access helps academics reach a broader, more diverse audience that includes the Global South and the general public.

Book publishing enables academics to disseminate their findings far and wide. Or so they hope. Many find their readership is actually quite limited due to the prohibitively high cost of hardback academic books and library subscription fees.

Geoffrey Khan is Regius Professor of Hebrew at the University of Cambridge, and general editor of the open access series Cambridge Semitic Languages and Cultures published by Open Book Publishers. His first books were published through traditional presses, and he was disappointed to realise how few copies sold.

He said:

“I was getting more and more frustrated with the lack of dissemination of the books. Disseminating academic research creates impact and publication is supposed to mean dissemination, but I wasn’t achieving that with traditional publishers.”

The switch to open access

Khan also realised that the cost of books and library subscriptions means that only wealthy universities – largely universities in the western world – can afford to buy books and access knowledge. As a result, many universities and academics are denied access to important research.

He decided to do something about it, setting up an open access series in his field. He began with his own book – The Tiberian Pronunciation Tradition of Biblical Hebrew, which won the 2021 Frank Moore Cross Book Award. Published open access about three years ago, take-up has been far greater than any of his previous works. Citations have also been far higher. Khan said:

“ It rapidly became clear that an incredible number of downloads were taking place, all over the world. The free on demand PDF was the big feature. So far it has been downloaded nearly 16,000 times. I sold under 100 books with my previous book.

Reaching a broader audience

Khan’s readership has also extended out of the Global North into the Global South. He is delighted that academics in less wealthy countries and institutions now have access. And to discover that the general public is also interested in his research.

He said:

“There is a genuine thirst for access to scholarship, a hunger for knowledge which goes beyond academic institutions. Academics have an important role to play in that, rather than being locked away in ivory towers.”

Preserving endangered languages and cultures

Some of the books in Khan’s series feature endangered languages and cultures, involving minority communities that have been displaced. Producing the research and disseminating it open access helps to preserve those languages and cultures and ensures that the communities where the research was conducted can have access to the research outcome.

Khan explains:

“It’s absolutely essential for these communities to get access to the documentation. Typically, in the past, scholars would do fieldwork in living communities and then publish an expensive book through traditional publishers, and no members of the community could afford to buy.”

Financing open access

Funding is a major challenge for the series. It's a not-for-profit initiative, but it does need to generate funds as many authors can't afford to pay to publish. Khan believes there should be many more initiatives like this – series run by academics in their field – but that there needs to be a way to secure regular funding beyond one-off grants and trust funds.

Khan set up a partnership between his university department and the not-for-profit open access publisher Open Book Publishers. Financial support for the series comes from various sources, including departmental trust funds, donations raised by Khan, grants of authors, and the open access library support scheme administered by Open Book Publishers. Compared to team-based research grants, the costs are relatively low. The series could be funded for 20 years or more for the average cost of a four-year team-based research project.